

DIFFERENT SOWING PERIODS OF MELON VARIETIES

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Abstract: *The results of the experiments showed that sowing periods has significant impact on growth and fertility of melon varieties. The sample seeds of varieties were sown at the specified sowing dates, and cultivated on the basis of generally accepted agro-technical measures under experiment. Biometric measurements were also performed in sowing experiments. The length of the main stem of the plant, the number and the length of the side branches were determined.*

Keywords: *experiment, seeds of variety samples, to sown, specified sowing period, melons, agro-technical measures*

Introduction: It is known that the yield and yield quality of melon varieties are directly related to the sowing period according to the early ripening group of the variety. Accordingly, the experiments were conducted to determine the optimal sowing period for the cultivation of early, middle and late ripening melon varieties in the Khorezm oasis, in 2018-2020.

Discussion: The seeds of early ripening Tarnak, Khandalik, Gurovak varieties were sown on April 15, April 20, April 25 and May 1 under experiment facilities. The seed variety of melon sown on April 20 was taken as a control sort and it was studied in comparison with other terms.

The seeds of medium-ripe Ok nov v ot, Kari kiz, Zargulobi varieties of melon were sown on May 5, May 10, May 15 and May 20. In this case, the samples sown on May 15 was chosen as a control medium.

The seeds of late-ripening Amudarya, Sahovat, Gulobi-Khorezmi melon varieties were sown on May 20, May 25, June 1 and June 5. In this case, the sample variety sown on May 25 was taken as a control medium and other varieties have been studied in comparison it.

Research methodology and outcome: Phenological observations

showed that the germination (10 and 75 percent), flowering (paternal and maternal flowers 10 and 75 percent) and fruit ripening of melon varieties differ depending on the sowing period.

It was noted that the total germination of seeds of early melon varieties under the experiment was by 75% within 12-15 days. It indicates that the seeds germinated much later due to the relatively low soil temperature from April 15 till May 1.

This physiological index was about 8-10 days, including 9-10 days in the varieties of Zargulobi and White nov vot, and 8-9 days in the variety of Kari-kiz In the middle-ripening varieties.

The seeds of late varieties sown on May 20 germinated faster, i.e. in 6-8 days, with 75% index in total as the soil temperature was high in that period of vegetation. Especially Gulobi Khorezmi melon seedlings sprouted the fastest, i.e. in 6-7 days.

The research studies of the blooming period of melon varieties showed that the appearance of the staminate flowers was earlier than the pistil flowers.

The research studies showed that the appearance of staminate flowers of early ripening varieties of melon happened after 32-34 days sown on May 1, while 37-38 days in varieties sown on April 15. However, this physiological value was 34-37 days in Ok Nov vot and Zargulobi varieties of the middle-ripening varieties of melon. It was noted that this feature was 40-45 days in the variety of Kari kiz sown on May 15-20 which is much later than others.

The staminate flowers of the late varieties of Amudarya melons sown on May 20 appeared in 39 days, while in the remaining varieties and in the sowing variants, they bloomed in 34-37 days.

The emergence of pistil flowers in early-ripening melon varieties in experimental variants was 38–43 days. The pistil flowers appeared in 44-45 days in the White Nov vot and Zargulobi middle-ripening varieties, and in Kari kiz variety sown on May 15-20, the index was very late, i.e. in 50-55 days. The pistil flowers of late variety appeared in 44-46 days, except the variety of Gulobi Khorezmi sown on June 5, with 75% blossom in 42 days.

The period of ripening of fruits was determined as a result of the experiment. And accordingly, the fruit of melon ripened in 70-82 days in all early ripening varieties of melons sown in above mentioned

period, while the fruit ripened in 75-90 in mid ripening varieties of melons sown in above mentioned period. And finally, it was 110-120 days for all sowing periods of late ripening varieties of melon

In the experiment on early ripening varieties sown on May 1 indicate that the Tarnak variety matured in 76 days, the Handalak variety in 75 days and the Gurovak variety in 70 days., it was noted that it ripened later in the remaining sowing periods. The earliest ripening of medium-ripe varieties was Zargulobi sown on May 5 and May 10 ripened in 75 days. The remaining varieties of other sowing periods ripen later, i.e. in 80-90 days.

This index was 110 days in late ripening varieties of melons as Amudarya sown on May 20, Sakhovat of May 25, and Gulobi Khorezmi of June 1 and 5. The late Amudarya variety under control sown on May 25 was the latest, i.e. the ripening period of the fruits was 120 days.

Biometric measurement results show that the length of the main stem of plants of early ripening varieties of melons was determined, and the longest stalk was 152-155 cm in the variants of Tarnak variety sown on April 25 and May 1, 170cm was in Gurovak sown on May 1.

The length of the main stem of the Handalak variety was 87-106 cm, i.e. relatively short at all planting periods,

This figure was 132-133 cm in mid ripening varieties of Zargulobi and Kari kiz sown on May 5 i.e. the lowest figure. It was 140-160 cm in the remaining periods.

The length of the main stem was of 138 cm with minimum index in late varieties of Sakhovat sown on May 20. It was found that the remaining varieties grew in the range of 144-170 cm in remaining sowing periods.

The data in the table also allowed to note that early varieties were characterized by relatively short stalks and late varieties were relatively long stalks regardless of the sowing period.

The highest indicator of the number of side branches in the biometric scale is the control variety of the mid ripening Kari Kiz variety in 4.0 pcs; the highest rate is 4.9 pcs in the control variety of late-ripening Amudarya variety sown on May 25 and 4.1-4.2 pcs in varieties sown on June 1 and 5 of it.

and control of the Sakhovat variety in the variants sown on May 25

and June 1, 5 was 4.0-4.2.

Relatively low branching, i.e. 3.1-3.2, was observed in medium ripening Zargulobi variety sown on May 5,10, In all other varieties and in all remaining sowing periods, the number of side branches had an average indication and varied in the range of 3.3–3.9.

According to the research outcome of measuring the length of the side branches in the experiment it was determined that the length of the side branches was 385-395 cm., i.e. the lowest in the variants of Tarnak and Guryak sown on April 15 from the early varieties.

The highest rate was found to be 615-633 cm in the control Handalak varieties sown on April 20, April 25 and May 1. It was found that this figure increased to 487-588 cm in the remaining varieties.

The lowest value of side branches length in mid-ripening varieties is 420-467 cm in Zargulobi sown on May 5 and 10, and it was 487 cm in Kari kyz variety sown on 5 May. The longest side branches were of the control variety of Ok Novvot sown on May 15 and May 20, which grew up to 636-644 cm. it was found that the side branches grew in the range of 515–595 cm in the remaining varieties.

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